

Adsorption behaviours of phenols onto modified activated carbon ECH derived from an agriculture waste (*Eleusine coracana* husk)

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Abstract : A low cost activated carbon derived from an aquatic plant *Eleusine coracana* husk (ECH) and modified by polymer Triton-X, was characterized for the removal of phenol and its derivatives (*p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol) from their aqueous solutions. The modified activated carbon ECH had micro porous and meso porous pore size distribution with surface area ($61.21 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and average pore width 7.48 nm. The Langmuir, Freundlich, Redlich-Peterson and Temkin models were applied to evaluate the adsorption parameters. The possible adsorption interactions were discussed. The effects of pH, urea and ionic strength on the adsorption also investigated. The adsorption mechanism is governed by complex interplay of electrostatic, π - π dispersive as well as by a charge transfer interaction. The adsorption decreased in the order of *p*-nitrophenol > *p*-chlorophenol > phenol. Thermodynamic study demonstrates an endothermic and spontaneous nature of adsorption. Adsorption kinetics was examined using different kinetics model (Lagergren first order, pseudo-second order and intra particle diffusion model). The best results were achieved with the Langmuir isotherm equilibrium model and followed pseudo-second order kinetics ($R^2 = 0.99$). The modified activated carbon ECH was found to be very effective for removal of phenols from their aqueous solutions.

Keywords : *Eleusine coracana* husk (ECH), modified activated carbon, phenols, adsorption, Triton-X.

Introduction

Phenol and its derivatives are hazardous materials for living beings¹, which are released into the aquatic environment by industries such as oil, gasoline, coal, paper, textile, petrochemicals, pharmaceuticals, phenolic resin, plastics, leather, tanning, wood, paint and fertilizer. Phenols cause taste and odor problems to drinking water² which invites many problems to human health including diarrhea, liver damage, anemia and dark urine³. There are various methods available for the treatment processes for phenols from wastewater such as chemical (oxidation, solvent extraction, irradiation, coagulation)^{4,5}, biological (accumulation, microbial degradation)⁶ and physical methods (adsorption, bioadsorption, activated carbon)⁷⁻¹¹. However, in recent years, adsorption systems have been widely employed in the purification of wastewater. The content of phenolic compounds in industrial wastewater (~ 200 – 2000 mg/L) is usually higher than the standard

limits (mostly 0.5 mg/L) established for their release into the aquatic environment¹². Consequently, extensive research work has been carried out using activated carbons and resins¹³. Many researchers^{9,14} have shown that activated carbon is an effective adsorbent for organic compounds, especially for phenol and its derivatives. However, activated carbon presents several disadvantages³⁰. The regeneration of saturated carbon is not economical and is accompanied by loss of the adsorbent. The use of commercial activated carbons based on relatively expensive starting materials is also unjustified for most pollution control applications³¹. In view of the above considerations, the search for a low cost and easily available adsorbent has led many investigators to seek relatively economic and efficient techniques using natural and vegetative adsorbents¹⁵⁻²¹. Raw agricultural solid wastes and waste materials from forest industries such as sawdust, rice husk, and bark, etc. have been used as adsorbents.

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These materials are available in large quantities and may have potential as adsorbents due to their physico-chemical characteristics and low-cost¹⁰. Extensive work has been devoted on the adsorption of phenolic compounds onto natural oxides, oxy (metal hydroxide), vegetative materials and onto carbon of commercial and agri-waste origin. Table 1 shows some recent and important references.

tion of organic molecules due to the preferential adsorption of water molecules. On the other hand, the absence of hydrophilic properties in an adsorbent makes its uniform distribution in the bulk of an aqueous solution impossible³³. Modifying the surface of an ECH with water soluble surfactant enables us not only to attain a desirable degree of hydrophilicity for the carbon particles but also

Table 1. A comparative study of phenols adsorption on vegetative adsorbents and commercial activated carbon

Substrate	Solute	Model	Capacity (mg/g)	
Commercial GAC	Phenol	Langmuir	350	Sulaymon and Ahmed ²²
Commercial GAC	Chlorophenol	Langmuir	319.9	Sulaymon and Ahmed ²²
Commercial PACT (power activated carbon treatment)	Phenol	Langmuir	135.7	Orshansky and Narkis ²³
Coconut-shell AC	4-Chlorophenol	Langmuir	72.8	Radhika and Palanivelu ²⁴
Coconut-shell AC	2,4,6-Trichlorophenol	Langmuir	122.3	Radhika and Palanivelu ²⁴
AC (from corncob)	Phenol	Langmuir	177.6	El-Hendawy <i>et al.</i> ²⁵
AC (from kraft black liquor)	Phenol	Langmuir	227	Gonzalez-Serranoa <i>et al.</i> ²⁶
AC (from kraft black liquor)	2,4,6-TCP	Langmuir	446	Gonzalez-Serranoa <i>et al.</i> ²⁶
Rice husk	Phenol	Langmuir	4.5	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Rice husk	4-NP	Langmuir	15.3	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Rice husk	4-CP	Langmuir	14.4	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Rice husk char	Phenol	Langmuir	7.9	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Rice husk char	4-NP	Freundlich	39.2	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Rice husk char	4-CP	Langmuir	36.2	Ahmaruzzaman and Sharma ²⁷
Red mud	2,4-DCP	Langmuir	130	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁸
Red mud	4-CP	Langmuir	127.1	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁸
Red mud	2-NP	Langmuir	117.3	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁸
Red mud	Phenol	Langmuir	59.2	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁸
BFA	Phenol	Langmuir	0.67	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁹
BFA	2-NP	Langmuir	1.15	Gupta <i>et al.</i> ²⁹
TBH	Phenol	Langmuir	97.52	Chandra and Singh ²¹
TBH	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	Langmuir	105.24	Chandra and Singh ²¹
TBH	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Langmuir	84.43	Chandra and Singh ²¹
Organomontmorillonite	Phenol	Langmuir	384.61	Jin <i>et al.</i> ⁵²
Bentonite	Phenol	Langmuir	66.67	Hank <i>et al.</i> ⁵³
Modified activated carbon ECH	Phenol	Langmuir	80.78	Present study
Modified activated carbon ECH	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	Langmuir	96.16	Present study
Modified activated carbon ECH	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Langmuir	98.05	Present study

The adsorption capacity of natural vegetative adsorbent may be improved by various modifications. The surfactant impregnation is one of the effective modification methods. The surfactant modified adsorbent alters the surface property of the adsorbent from hydrophilicity to hydrophobicity³². The presence of hydrophilic regions (polar region) on the surface of ECH lowers the adsorp-

tion to control the degree and the rate of their dispersive ability in aqueous media³⁴. Functionalized group Triton X-100 is a nonionic surfactant that has a hydrophilic polyethylene oxide chain and an aromatic hydrocarbon hydrophobic group. The hydrocarbon group is a 4-phenyl group. The objective of the present work was to evaluate the analytical potential of modified activated carbon ECH

for effective removal of phenol and its derivatives from their aqueous solutions. The physical and chemical properties of the modified activated carbon ECH were evaluated and the effect of solution pH, temperature, urea and ionic strength on adsorption was studied.

Experimental

All reagents used were AR grade chemicals. Stock solutions of the test solution were made by dissolving pyridine in double distilled water. The pH of the test solutions was adjusted using dilute HCl (0.1 N) and NaOH (0.1 N). The modified activated carbon ECH was derived from an inexpensive, abundantly available and eco-friendly source.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy : The modified activated carbon ECH (2 mg) was mixed with 200 mg of KBr and then pelleted. The FT-IR spectra of the pellets were recorded using a Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectrometer (FTIR) of ThermoScientific (Nicole 6700).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) : The particle morphologies of the modified activated carbon ECH were studied using scanning electron microscope of JEOL (JSM 6490 LV). Samples were mounted on aluminum stab with the help of double-sided tape. Mounted stabs were coated with carbon palladium prior to analysis using a Polaron sputter coater.

Point of zero charge (PZC) for functionalized ECH : The PZC characteristic of functionalized ECH was determined by solid addition method using 0.1 M KCl and 0.002 M citrimide solutions. KCl and citrimide solution (40 ml) was taken in 100 ml Stoppered conical flask. Cetrimide is used as a stabilizing reagent. The initial pH values of the solutions were roughly adjusted between 2 and 12 by adding either 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH. The total volume of the solution in each flask was adjusted exactly to 50 ml by adding the KCl and citrimide solution. The initial pH of the solution was then accurately noted. The modified activated carbon ECH (0.5 g) was added to each flask. The suspensions were shaken and allowed to equilibrate for two days with intermittent shaking. The final pH values of the supernatant liquid were noted. The difference between the initial and final pH

values ($\Delta\text{pH} = \text{pH}_i - \text{pH}_f$) were plotted against the initial pH value. The point of intersection of the resulting curve at which change in pH is zero gives the PZC.

Preparation of modified activated carbon ECH : The straw of *Eleusine coracana* obtained from the hill area of Uttarakhand (India) was used as a precursor for modified activated carbon ECH employing HNO₃ activation method. The oxidizing agent (HNO₃) was used for the impregnation oxygen on the surface of ECH to form carbon-oxygen functional groups¹⁴. The raw material was washed with tap water to remove any ashes on the surface, dried and crushed in a pestle and motors. The dried mass was immersed in 35 wt% HNO₃ at a ratio of 3 : 1 over 12 h at 60 °C, followed by carbonization and activation at 720 °C in a muffle furnace carried out in inert atmosphere for 1 h. After cooling, the produced material was washed several times with distilled water until a constant near neutral pH was observed, then dried at 85 °C for 8 h, cooled to room temperature, and sieved to the desired particle size by standard sieves. The product was referred to as *Eleusine coracana* husk (ECH). About 5.0 g of husk was added to 250 ml of 1.0 mol/L Triton-X in a conical flask and stirred for 24 h at room temperature for 5 days was filtered and washed thoroughly with distilled water and finally washed with acetone. The product obtained was dried at 350 °C for 24 h, ground to a fine powder and labeled as modified activated carbon ECH.

Adsorption procedure : The adsorption equilibrium was probed by batch technique in 250 ml conical flasks contacting the modified activated carbon ECH (1.0 g/L) with 100 ml of phenol solutions of known concentrations (25–1000 mg/L), shaking at 100 rpm for 2 h at room temperature (30 °C), followed by filtration (0.45 μ) and subsequent analysis of residual phenol concentration in the filtrate (double beam spectrophotometer Carry-100, Australia) at 269, 280 and 322 nm, (λ_{max}) respectively. The effect of adsorbent dose, adsorbate concentration, temperature, pH and effect of urea was investigated. For determining the effect of pH on phenol adsorption, initial pH of phenol solutions were adjusted to the desired value (2–10) using 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH. The amount of phenols adsorbed by the adsorbent at equilibrium was calculated as follows :

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

where C_0 and C_e are initial and equilibrium concentrations (mg L^{-1}) of phenols in the solution, V the volume (L), m the weight (g) of the adsorbent and q_e is the amount of phenols adsorbed by the adsorbent at equilibrium (mg g^{-1}).

Results and discussion

Elemental characterization : The elemental analysis of the modified activated carbon ECH is mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2. Elemental analysis of modified activated carbon ECH

Element	% Composition
C	31.61
O	43.92
Na	0.75
Mg	2.34
Al	0.11
Si	12.06
P	2.36
K	1.79
Ca	4.90
Mn	0.10
Fe	0.06

FT-IR analysis : The FT-IR spectrum of blank modified activated carbon ECH (Fig. 1) showed weak and broad peaks in the region of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which showed the presence of hydroxyl, carbonyl, carboxyl, lactone, aromatic, and cellulosic groups. The band stretch observed in FT-IR spectrum of the functionalized ECH at 3671 and 3745 cm^{-1} are typically of cellulosic -OH groups²⁰. Similarly, the characteristic broad peak of carboxylic -OH at 3431 cm^{-1} and the band stretch at 1652 cm^{-1} showed the presence of carboxylate group²⁰, which shifted to 1651 , 1650 cm^{-1} after the adsorption of *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol respectively. The other specific area identified in the blank modified activated carbon ECH was at 1215.6 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of lactone, which shifted to 1210 cm^{-1} after the adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol due to hydrogen bonding. These observations indicate the formation of carbonyl groups on modified activated carbon ECH. It has been re-

ported^{21,35} that oxidized carbon contains mainly carboxyl, hydroxyl and carbonyl groups. The possible mechanism for phenols adsorption onto modified activated carbon ECH was postulated on the basis of functional groups evident from the FT-IR spectral analysis of blank and phenols-adsorbed modified activated carbon ECH. It may be concluded that adsorption of phenols onto modified activated carbon ECH was through hydrogen bonding mechanism in which functional group of aromatic compounds (-OH, -Cl and -NO₂) may play a very important role. The functional groups of aromatic ring may form hydrogen bonding with the carbonyl and hydroxyl group of the modified activated carbon ECH which is responsible for occurrence of adsorption.

SEM analysis : The SEM images shown in Fig. 2 clearly demonstrate the porosity and surface texture of new adsorbent material. The smooth appearance of the modified activated carbon ECH surface is due to the result of the doping of the nonionic surfactant (Triton-X).

BET analysis : Surface area and pore characteristics of adsorbents modified activated carbon ECH were determined from nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms at 77 °K using a surface area analyzer (BELSORP-max, Japan) shown in Fig. 3. The BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) surface area (S_{BET}) and average pore diameter (R_{avg}) were measured by means of standard BET equation applied in the relative pressure range of $0.05\text{--}0.10$. The total pore volume (V_p) and pore radius (R_p) were deduced from the manufacturer's software shown in Table 3.

PZC characterization : The surface potential of the adsorbent may be influenced by the pH value³⁶ of the coexisting liquid bulk phase. The pH value at which the surface charge is zero is called the point of zero charge (PZC) given in Fig. 4. The surface is positively charged at $\text{pH} < \text{pH}_{\text{PZC}}$ and negatively charged at $\text{pH} > \text{pH}_{\text{PZC}}$. Since, pH_{PZC} of the modified activated carbon ECH was determined and found to be about 6.8, at any $\text{pH} < \text{pH}_{\text{PZC}}$, the surface of modified activated carbon ECH is positively charged and at $\text{pH} > \text{pH}_{\text{PZC}}$, the surface is negative.

Adsorption equilibrium : Several equilibrium isotherm equations were applied to optimize of an adsorption system for the adsorption of phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH.

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of adsorbed with and without phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH.

Fig. 2. SEM images of modified activated carbon ECH at different magnifications.

Fig. 3. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms and BJH plot of modified activated carbon ECH.

Table 3. Surface parameters of modified activated carbon ECH

(V _{mono}) (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	(S _{BET}) (m ² g ⁻¹)	(V _T) (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	R _{avg} (nm)	R _p (nm)
14.06	61.21	0.032	7.47	1.21

The Freundlich isotherm³⁷ is employed by assuming a heterogeneous surface with a nonuniform distribution of heat of adsorption over the surface may be written as :

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

where q_e (mg/g) is the amount of solute adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent, C_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium concentration of solute, K_F (mg/g) is the Freundlich constant which indicate the relative adsorption capacity of the adsorbent and $1/n$ is the constant indicate the intensity of adsorption.

The Langmuir equilibrium isotherm³⁸ is based on the fact that the adsorption occurs at specific homogeneous site within the surface of adsorbent and monolayer sorption onto a surface with a finite number of identical sites and there are no interaction between adsorbed molecules on the surface, may be written as :

$$q_e = \frac{q_m K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (3)$$

where q_e (mg/g) is the amount of solute adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent, C_e (mg/L) is the equilibrium concentration of solute, q_m is the monolayer adsorption capacity (mg/g) and is a constant, and K_L is a constant related to the free energy of sorption ($K_L \propto e^{-\Delta G/RT}$). It is the reciprocal of the concentration at which the adsorbent is half-saturated.

The Redlich-Peterson³⁹ (R-P) equation is a three parameter model and can be applied to homogeneous and heterogeneous system and given as :

$$q_e = \frac{K_R C_e}{1 + a_r C_e^\beta} \quad (4)$$

where K_R (L/g) and a_r (L/mg) is R-P isotherm constant and β is the exponent having values between 0 and 1. Since K_R is unknown in linear R-P equation which can be fitted to experimental data by maximizing R^2 (regression coefficient) between predicted value of q_e and the experi-

Fig. 4. Point of zero charge (PZC) of the modified activated carbon ECH by solid addition method.

mental data using the solver add-in function of datafit-9 program.

The Temkin isotherm⁴⁰ is given as :

$$q_e = \frac{RT}{b} \ln (K_T C_e) \quad (5)$$

where $B_1 = RT/b$, b is the Temkin energy constant ($J \text{ mol}^{-1}$). The factor K_T in this isotherm explicitly takes into account the interactions between adsorbing species and the adsorbent.

The standard deviation and standard error in each case was determined using the equation :

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}} \quad (6)$$

and

Fig. 5. Plots illustrating different isotherms for phenol, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol adsorption onto the modified activated carbon ECH at 30 °C.

$$\text{standard error} = s/n \quad (7)$$

where s is standard deviation, n is the total number of samples, \bar{x} is the average of the sample, \bar{x} is the value of each sample.

The comparative nonlinear plots for phenols using different isotherm models given in Fig. 5, clearly showed that the Langmuir isotherm model was found best fitted among studied models.

The linear and non linear regression coefficient showed that the Langmuir model was better fitted model in the sorption behavior of phenols from the aqueous solution onto the modified activated carbon ECH than other adsorption isotherm models. It was assumed that the monolayer sorption takes place onto an adsorbent surface with a finite number of identical homogeneous sites defined by Langmuir equation. Different isotherm parameters were tabulated in Table 4.

Kinetics of adsorption : Adsorption kinetics was studied by monitoring the progress of the adsorption process at different time intervals. Fig. 6 clearly demonstrates that the amount of adsorption was found to steeply increase up to nearly 15 min and the equilibration time for the studied phenolic compounds is 80 min within the experimental errors. Several kinetic models were tested with observed experimental results in order to describe the mechanism of adsorption process. The results of the applied models are represented on the Fig. 7. The kinetic parameters of each model are tabulated in Table 5.

The Lagergren first order rate expression⁴¹ is written as :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t \quad (8)$$

where q_t and q_{eq} are the amount adsorbed at time t and at

Table 4. Different isotherm parameters for phenol, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol adsorption onto the modified activated carbon ECH at 30 °C

Parameters	Phenol	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenol	<i>p</i> -Nitro-phenol
Langmuir isotherm			
K_L (L/mg)	4.90×10^{-2}	4.47×10^{-2}	7.27×10^{-2}
q_m (mg/g)	80.78	96.16	98.05
R^2 (non linear)	0.98	0.98	0.99
Standard error	3.01	4.11	3.67
Freundlich isotherm			
K_f [(mg/g) (L/mg) ⁿ]	14.22	14.71	20.43
n	0.34	0.37	0.30
R^2 (non linear)	0.90	0.90	0.92
Standard error	6.86	8.42	8.97
Temkin isotherm			
B_1 (J mol ⁻¹)	17.84	22.03	18.96
K_T (L/mg)	0.45	0.34	0.76
R^2 (non linear)	0.96	0.96	0.957
Standard error	4.34	5.15	6.03
Redlich-Peterson model			
K_R (L/g)	4.19	10.67	21.42
a_R (L/mg)	9.33	16.03	2.84
β	0.86	0.97	0.75
R^2 (non linear)	0.98	0.98	0.98
Standard error	3.04	3.96	4.17

Fig. 6. A plot of q_t vs time (min).

equilibrium, t is time K_1 is rate constant for adsorption.

A $\log (q_e - q_t)$ vs time plots give a straight line (Fig. 7). K_1 was calculated from the slope at different

temperature and data are presented in Table 5.

The pseudo-second order kinetic equation⁴¹ is given as :

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = K_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (9a)$$

The integration of the equation leads to :

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} t \quad (9b)$$

where K_2 is the rate constant ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$).

The slope and intercept of the plot between t/q_t vs $1/t$ gives the value of q_e and K_2 , respectively and are shown in Table 5.

The intra-particle diffusion equation is expressed as :

$$q_t = K_p t^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where K_p ($\text{mg/g-min}^{1/2}$) is the intra-particle diffusion rate constant. A plot of q_t vs $t^{1/2}$ gives the value of K_p and are shown in Table 5.

From Table 5 it is found that the first order kinetic equation, the value of q_e are not in agreement with the experimental (q_{exp}) and regression coefficient ($R^2 = 0.97$), and does not follow Lagergeren first order satisfactorily. However, the second order kinetic model represents the adsorption data well with $R^2 = 0.99$. In the intra-particle diffusion model (Fig. 7), the initial portion represents external rapid diffusion stage (the film diffusion). The second linear portion is the particle diffusion controlled by intra-particle diffusion¹⁸, however; intra-particle diffusion model does not properly suit to observed data. It was concluded that the adsorption of phenols on modified activated carbon ECH does not follow intra-particle diffusion model satisfactorily. Such representative plots are shown in Fig. 7.

Effect of surface functionalities and pH of solution : It has been reported¹⁴ that in solution, phenols behave as weak acid ($\text{p}K_a$ of phenol, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol are 9.89, 9.37 and 7.15, respectively). The initial pH of adsorption medium is one of the most important parameters affecting the adsorption process. At $\text{pH} \geq 10$, the phenols dissociate and phenolate anions are formed, while the surface functional groups are either neutral or negatively charged^{42,43}. The electrostatic repulsion between

Fig. 7. Different kinetic models for the adsorption of phenols onto modified activated carbon ECH : (a) Lagergeren plot, (b) pseudo-second order plot and (c) intra-particle diffusion plot.

Table 5. Kinetics parameters for adsorption of phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH

Lagergeren model				
	K_1 (min^{-1})	q_e (mg/g)	Standard error	R^2
Phenol	0.061	100.72	0.1862	0.96
Chlorophenol	0.053	32.36	0.1452	0.97
Nitrophenol	0.054	38.48	0.1083	0.98
Kinetic model of the pseudo-second order				
	K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	q_e (mg/g)	Standard error	R^2
Phenol	0.0031	62.5	0.028	0.999
Chlorophenol	0.0021	68.07	0.014	0.999
Nitrophenol	0.0027	71.42	0.021	0.999
Intra-particle diffusion				
	K_p	Standard error	R^2	
Phenol	2.61	1.71	0.97	
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	2.16	2.94	0.90	
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	2.31	3.11	0.90	

Fig. 8. The effect of pH of studied phenols on modified activated carbon.

the identical charges lowers the adsorption capacities in the case of phenol, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-nitrophenol. The effect of pH can also be explained using pH_{ZPC} of the adsorbent. In the present study, the pH_{ZPC} of modified activated carbon ECH is 6.8. At any pH below pH_{ZPC} , the surface of the adsorbent is positively charged and at pH above pH_{ZPC} , the surface is negatively charged. The adsorption of phenols on modified activated carbon ECH shows that adsorption decreases with increasing pH (Fig. 8). The pH primarily affects the degree of ionization of phenols and the surface properties of the modified activated carbon ECH. At low pH values, the surface of modified activated carbon ECH would be protonated and resulted in a stronger attraction for aromatic ring and electronegative group of phenols. At high pH, OH^- ions

would compete with the phenolate ion for sorption sites⁴⁴. Sorption of excess of OH^- ions could convert an initial positively charged surface of modified activated carbon ECH into a negatively charged surface resulting repulsion of negatively charged phenolates ions and thus adsorption decreased. This could also be due to the increased solubility of phenol in alkaline conditions, which results in greater affinity for the phenol molecules to remain in solution rather than to get adsorbed onto the carbon surface. Unionized phenol molecules would also be attracted, possibly, by physical force (H-bonding).

When the solution pH is lowered than pH_{ZPC} , the undissociated phenols molecules are more easily attracted by the positively charged surface of adsorbent, favoring the accumulation of phenols molecules on the surface and thus promoting adsorption. On the other hand, when the solution pH exceeded pH_{ZPC} , the phenolate ions are repelled by the negative charged surface of adsorbent, hence, adsorption is decreased⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷.

It was observed that modified activated carbon ECH has a maximum affinity toward phenols at pH ~ 6.0 to 8.0. It appears that the dominant sorption process takes place in molecular forms of phenols at lower pH is perhaps given by eq. (11(a)). Other reactions given by eq. (11(b)) plays

gives the value of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 , respectively⁵⁰. Where R (8.314 J/K-mol) is the universal gas constant, T (K) is the absolute temperature.

The Van't Hoff plot is shown in Fig. 9. The thermodynamic data are presented in Table 6.

The endothermic nature of the adsorption was con-

Table 6. Thermodynamics parameters for adsorption of phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH

Isotherm equation	ΔH^0 (kJ/mol)	ΔS^0 (kJ/mol K)	$-\Delta G^0$ (kJ/mol)				
			283 K	293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K
Phenol	6.18	0.031	2.59	2.90	3.21	3.52	3.83
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	9.10	0.041	2.50	2.91	3.23	3.73	4.14
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	12.76	0.083	10.73	11.56	12.39	13.22	14.05

an insignificant role in the overall adsorption of phenol onto the modified activated carbon ECH.

Thermodynamics of titled adsorbate-adsorbent system :

The effect of temperature on the adsorption behavior of the modified activated carbon ECH has been studied in the range of 283–313 K. At very low temperature i.e. 283 K, the adsorption phenomenon was very slow, at moderate temperature (303–313 K) adsorptions gradually increases and then constant at 323 K. It is anticipated that temperature is required for the breaking of hydrogen bonding between phenols and water molecules which first enhanced the rate of adsorption at moderate temperature. Data (Table 6) demonstrates an endothermic nature of the process. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated as follows :

Gibbs free energy change ΔG^0 was calculated⁴⁸ using the equation $\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_L$

where K_L is the Langmuir constant at temperature 303 K. Since, the Langmuir isotherm has been found to well represented ($R^2 = 0.99$) the equilibrium sorption data. The Langmuir constant K_L (L/mg) has been used to determine the thermodynamic parameters from given eqs. :

The Gibbs free energy⁴⁹ change is also related to enthalpy and entropy as :

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0 \quad (12)$$

Apparent heat of adsorption enthalpy, ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 was evaluated using the equation :

$$\ln K_L = \frac{-\Delta G^0}{RT} = \frac{\Delta S^0}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^0}{RT} \quad (13)$$

The slope and intercept of the plot between $\ln K_L$ vs $1/T$

Fig. 9. Van't Hoff plots for studied phenols.

firming by the thermodynamic parameters as shown in Table 6. The negative value of ΔG^0 is an indication of the spontaneous nature of the process. Apparent enthalpy of adsorption, ΔH^0 also confirms the endothermic nature of the adsorption process.

Effect of ionic strength : In the present study, the influence of the ionic strength on the amount of the adsorption was investigated (Fig. 10). It is anticipated that the hydrophobic force could be the primary driving force for the adsorption of phenol onto modified activated carbon ECH. If a hydrophobic interaction makes a significant contribution to adsorption of phenol onto modified activated carbon ECH, the adsorption density would have increased with the addition of salt due to "salting out effect"^{51,52}. It was found that the adsorption capacity of phenols exhibits an appreciable increase with addition of

Fig. 10. Plots showing the effect of ionic strength of adsorption of phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH at 303 K, pH = 7.0.

KCl. A possible cause is the adsorption of H₂O onto adsorbent. Due to the presence of hydroxyl groups in adsorbent, water cluster might be formed on the surface by hydrogen bonding, which can interface the adsorption of phenols. In the presence of KCl, water cluster can be demolished. Hence, the adsorption capacity of phenols increases.

Effect of urea : To explore the role of hydrogen bonding, adsorption tests were executed in the presence of urea, a hydrogen bond breaker⁵². Adsorption was reduced in the presence of urea (shown in Fig. 11) suggesting the role of hydrogen bonding in the present case.

Fig. 11. Plots showing the effect of ionic strength of adsorption of phenols onto the modified activated carbon ECH at 303 K, pH = 7.0.

Conclusions

Modified activated carbon ECH; produced from *Eleusine coracana* (waste of ragi) demonstrates high po-

tential for effective removal of phenol and its derivatives from waste water compared to various commercial and vegetative adsorbent (given in Table 1). Since the cost of adsorbent is one of the crucial and important factors to know the economic feasibility of the process, the precursor of modified activated carbon ECH is an agriculture waste materials and its cost was negligible. The various equilibrium models such as Freundlich, Langmuir, Redlich-Peterson and Temkin were tested to describe the equilibrium adsorption. However, Langmuir isotherm was found most suitable as representative of the equilibrium adsorption data. The kinetic modeling of the phenols adsorption onto modified activated carbon ECH indicates that adsorption process is pseudo-second order with the correlation coefficients higher than 0.99. Thermodynamic calculations indicate that the sorption process is spontaneous and endothermic. The adsorption properties of studied adsorption system depend on several factors such as pK_a , polarity and solution condition such as pH, ionic strength and adsorbate concentration. The adsorption mechanism is governed by complex interplay of electrostatic, π - π dispersive as well as by the charge transfer interaction. The precursor employed for the preparation of the activated carbon (modified activated carbon ECH) is widely available and inexpensive. Hence, scalable for industrial purpose.

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